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A Knowledge-Driven Framework for a Decision Support Platform in Sustainable Viticulture: Integrating Climate Data and Supporting Stakeholder Collaboration

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Abstract: Viticulture in Montenegro faces significant challenges due to fragmented data management, limited access to high-resolution climate predictions, and the lack of systematic integration between stakeholders. This study addresses these issues by proposing a knowledge-driven system architecture that consolidates climate and phenology data, facilitates multi-level data sharing, and supports informed decision-making for sustainable vineyard management. Using Montenegro as a case study, the proposed decision support platform integrates data from Internet of Things-enabled climate pilots, existing databases, and predictive modeling tools to address limitations in existing datasets, such as low resolution and inaccurate downscaling methods, and to tackle the broader challenges posed by climate change, including shifting weather patterns and phenological cycles. The system architecture provides a framework for stakeholders, including researchers, winegrowers, and policymakers, to collaborate effectively, bridging the gap between localized data collection and high-level decision-making. The paper outlines the current state of viticulture in Montenegro and the EU, highlights the need for a systematic approach to data management, and details the benefits of such a system at various levels. The proposed platform architecture and implementation steps outlined in this study serve as a robust framework, offering valuable guidance for other countries seeking to establish similar systems to enhance the efficiency, sustainability, and resilience of their viticulture sectors. This research contributes to the broader understanding of knowledge-driven systems in precision agriculture and provides a scalable model for regions facing similar challenges.

Keywords: decision support platform; viticulture; vineyard management; climate data; phenology; IoT; sustainability

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1. Introduction

Viticulture is a crucial sector in Montenegro, deeply rooted in the country's history and cultural identity, while also contributing significantly to its economy [1–3]. It is centered around the Plantaže vineyard, which spans over 2300 ha as the largest European vineyard in a single complex [4]. In addition to this prominent vineyard, numerous smaller family-owned vineyards play an essential role in the country's diverse and high-quality wine production. The majority of vineyard production in Montenegro is dedicated to red grape varieties, which account for approximately 70% of the total production, with Vranac being

the dominant variety. However, the industry faces mounting challenges, including the effects of climate change, such as more erratic weather patterns, shifts in grapevine growth cycles, and increased vulnerability to pests and diseases [5,6]. The total land area covered by vineyards in Montenegro in 2023 was 2719.8 ha, with a total production of 16,283.0 tons of grapes and the yield per vine on plantations of 1.4 kilograms, both with a consistent decrease over past years [7]. These issues are compounded by Montenegro's unique geographic characteristics, where mountainous terrain and microclimates [8] demand highly localized data to support precision viticulture [9,10]. Multiple microclimates within a small geographical area are induced by dramatic elevations and varied landscapes creating unique environmental conditions across short distances. Based on the study of viticulture zoning, Montenegro's viticultural geographical production areas are divided into classified viticultural regions and potential viticultural regions, as displayed in Figure 1 [11].

Part of the vineyards are nestled in the region of the Montenegrin coast [12]. Inland, in the mountainous terrain, lie the regions of Nudo, Montenegrin North, and the largest, the Montenegrin Basin of Lake Skadar. These thrive amidst a complex topography, and diversifying microclimates. According to viticulture zoning studies, rising temperatures are expected to enable new regions, such as Bijelo Polje, Nikšić, and Dragaljsko Polje, spanning a total area of 70 km², to thrive in the future [9,11]. These areas will support the cultivation of grape varieties such as Cabernet Sauvignon and Nebbiolo under the projected climate conditions [13]. Despite its importance, existing climate datasets are often too coarse to capture these local variations effectively, leaving growers without the actionable insights needed for sustainable vineyard management.

Figure 1. Current and future viticultural regions in Montenegro.

At the same time, the European Union has emphasized sustainability in viticulture as part of its broader environmental and climate initiatives, within different key initiatives, such as the Farm to Fork Strategy, the EU Biodiversity Strategy for 2030, and Common Agricultural Policy [14–16]. This creates an opportunity to align Montenegro's efforts with

those of larger viticultural regions, but resource constraints, fragmented data systems, and limited cooperation between key stakeholders remain significant obstacles. This situation highlights the need for systematic approaches to managing data and fostering collaboration among researchers, winegrowers, and policymakers. Furthermore, according to International Organization of Vine and Wine, precision viticulture is a cyclic management approach to field operations based on information and technology tools that uses multiple sources of vineyard-related data to support site specific decision making with the aim to optimize production processes [10]. Taking this into account, both sustainability and precision viticulture would benefit from a unified platform usage.

One of the core challenges for Montenegro is the reliance on global climate datasets like CHELSA [17], which often lack the spatial resolution needed to provide meaningful insights for a small, topographically complex country. Attempts to improve these datasets through downscaling have often resulted in inaccuracies, creating further difficulties in decision-making for vineyard management. Although CHELSA is considered to be the most reliable comparing to E-OBS [18] and ERA5-Land [19] datasets, results still indicate that localized weather data are necessary for an effective system in such geographical habitat. For example, Fernandes et al. [9] compared 30-year averages of monthly precipitation at the Podgorica weather station, with data from CHELSA [17], E-OBS [18], and ERA5-Land [19], finding overestimations of 49 mm, 19 mm and 20 mm, respectively, so precipitation data are hard to validate [20].

Water availability is essential for viticulture, and is driven by precipitation patterns and water intake [21]. Increasing water demands and changes in precipitation patterns can lead to drought [22]. Future projections suggest changes in the precipitation patterns [5], and such significantly influence phenological phases, directly affecting crop yields [23–25]. For instance, inconsistent rainfall can disrupt phenological phases such as flowering, fruit set and berries developing leading to reduced productivity [24,26]. Droughts can result in reduced yields, as they affect various yield-related parameters, particularly berry size and bud fertility [27]. Similarly, elevated temperatures can accelerate phenological stages, leading to earlier bud break, flowering, and ripening [24]. This advancement often shortens the growing period, potentially affecting grape quality and yield [28]. For instance, a study on grapevines in Mendoza, Argentina, demonstrated that increased temperatures advanced phenological stages and altered physiological responses, impacting overall yield [29]. Similarly, research has shown that higher temperatures can lead to earlier flowering and maturity, often resulting in decreased grape yield due to reduced berry development periods [30,31]. Consequently, it is essential to collect and predict accurate precipitation and temperature data, among other, in order to provide a good base for prediction and effective mitigation and adaptation strategies. However, no centralized system exists in Montenegro to collect, process, and integrate diverse data sources, such as Internet of Things (IoT) sensors, phenological data, and climate projections, into a single, coherent framework that can guide decisions at multiple levels, such as researchers seeking insights for predictive modeling, vineyard managers optimizing operations, and policymakers developing sustainable strategies.

Climate change is causing noticeable shifts in precipitation patterns and rising temperatures, which are directly impacting viticulture across Europe, including in Montenegro [32,33]. In this region, warmer temperatures are accelerating grape ripening, potentially leading to higher sugar content but lower acidity in wines, which can alter their balance and quality [34]. Changes in rainfall, with longer dry spells and more intense storms, are increasing the risk of water stress and soil erosion in vineyards. Montenegro's traditional grape varieties, such as Vranac and Krstač [35], are particularly susceptible to these conditions, which may challenge the sustainability of local wine production. Adapting to these

changes will require innovative irrigation strategies, improved soil management [36] and careful selection of resilient grape varieties to safeguard Montenegro's viticultural heritage [37]. This fragmentation underscores the need for a holistic approach that leverages technology and systematic data integration to address these gaps. Such a solution would provide stakeholders across the value chain with access to accurate, actionable information, improving sustainability and resilience in the face of climate change.

The impact of climate change on viticulture is profound, presenting significant challenges to grape quality, yield, and the economic stability of wine production. As temperatures rise, precipitation patterns shift and extreme weather events become more frequent, the viticulture sector becomes increasingly vulnerable to environmental stresses that disrupt traditional cultivation practices. Efficient adaptation and mitigation strategies are imperative to address these challenges, and their success depends on the adoption of systemic approaches that foster cross-sectoral communication and collaboration among policymakers, stakeholders, researchers, and viticulturists. Since the 1980s, the need for decision support systems (DSSs) in agricultural crop management has grown considerably [38], leading to the development of numerous DSSs designed to assist extension agents, consultants and growers in making informed decisions based on real-time data and scientific modeling [39].

Building on this trend and recognizing the critical importance of addressing climate change in viticulture, Europe has undertaken a range of initiatives to address the multifaceted challenges posed by a warming climate. These efforts include the implementation of targeted projects and policies that focus on understanding climate impacts and developing DSSs to facilitate informed and sustainable vineyard management.

One prominent initiative, Sustainable Viticulture for Climate Change Adaptation (LIFE VineAdapt) [40], is a cross-regional project that emphasizes the promotion of vineyard practices designed to enhance resilience to climate change. Operating across several European countries, the initiative connects viticulturists, environmental organizations, and policymakers in a collaborative framework. Through this collaboration, the project has successfully implemented adaptive vineyard techniques such as water-efficient irrigation, soil conservation practices and climate-adapted grape varieties. It has further monitored these practices' efficacy and shared the findings widely to encourage adoption across diverse viticultural landscapes. Similarly, the ADVICLIM [41] project in France adopts a science-driven approach to adaptation by integrating cutting-edge climate modeling with active stakeholder engagement. ADVICLIM enables researchers, winegrowers and local authorities to work together to assess the regional impacts of climate change on vineyards and develop robust adaptation strategies. These efforts have resulted in actionable insights that inform vineyard management practices while influencing regional policy decisions to ensure long-term resilience.

In Spain, VineSens [42] exemplifies the role of eco-smart technology in addressing climate change impacts on viticulture. This advanced DSS employs a wireless sensor network to monitor critical environmental parameters, including temperature, humidity, and soil moisture. By incorporating epidemiological models, VineSens forecasts the risk of vineyard diseases such as downy mildew, providing growers with real-time alerts and recommendations to mitigate potential outbreaks. The platform's intuitive web interface makes it accessible to a wide range of users, from vine growers to agricultural advisors, fostering a data-driven approach to disease prevention. Another Spanish initiative, a DSS for Irrigation Scheduling in Agriculture, tackles the pressing issue of water scarcity by optimizing irrigation practices [43]. This system integrates soil moisture data, weather forecasts, and predictive models to determine the optimal timing and amount of irrigation, significantly enhancing water use efficiency. These advancements support sustainable

vineyard management while benefiting both growers and policymakers by contributing to the efficient allocation of scarce water resources.

Despite these significant advancements in Europe, Montenegro faces a marked absence of such systemic approaches. Recent studies have highlighted the considerable challenges Montenegrin viticulture is experiencing due to climate change [9]. These include rising temperatures and altered precipitation patterns—all of which threaten the viability of traditional grape varieties and the economic sustainability of the region's wine industry. The lack of integrated platforms, collaborative frameworks, and advanced tools exacerbates these challenges, leaving Montenegrin viticulture ill-prepared to adapt to the ongoing climate crisis. This situation underscores the urgent need for developing systems that bridge the gap between policymakers, researchers and viticulturists in Montenegro. Such systems would enable the integration of scientific research, technological tools and stakeholder collaboration to build resilience against climate change impacts. By fostering a holistic approach to adaptation and mitigation, Montenegro could ensure the long-term sustainability of its viticulture sector, preserving its cultural heritage and economic significance while contributing to the global effort to combat the effects of climate change. The knowledge and initiative for such an approach came within an ongoing three-year Horizon Europe MONTEVITIS project, in which Montenegro is collaborating with five European partners to develop a unified strategy [44]. This initiative fosters joint efforts and creates synergies across borders. MONTEVITIS also includes four Montenegrin family winery partners who have actively contributed to the project and demonstrated their eagerness to implement new strategies, as evidenced by the successful testing of the MONTEVITIS application for phenological phases. As an outcome of this ongoing project, a foundation for knowledge sharing and innovation has also been established.

In the scope of viticulture, previous studies are mostly based on enology analysis and genetic profiles. Our research is a novelty to Montenegro, and crucial for the sector. It proposes a unified knowledge-based platform designed to address the unique challenges of Montenegro's viticulture sector by integrating advanced technologies and fostering collaboration across stakeholders. This decision support platform (DSP) is designed to combine high-resolution climate data collected through IoT-enabled devices with existing datasets and predictive modeling tools, offering a unified system to improve decision-making processes. By seamlessly integrating diverse data sources, the platform addresses the fragmented data management that currently hinders sustainable practices in viticulture. Beyond its technical capabilities, the DSP establishes a collaborative ecosystem that connects researchers, vineyard managers, and policymakers, facilitating a continuous exchange of information to promote sustainability and resilience in vineyard management. The study first assesses the current state of viticulture in Montenegro, comparing it with broader practices in the EU to highlight existing gaps. The system architecture design of the DSP is presented, showcasing its capacity to integrate diverse datasets and provide actionable insights. This study also explores implementation strategies and the multi-level benefits of this system, offering a replicable framework for other regions facing similar challenges and underscoring the importance of knowledge-driven solutions in advancing precision agriculture.

The research is structured to systematically address the integration of phenological and environmental data into vineyard management. It focuses on the development and implementation of a unified platform to collect, process, and analyze global and local data, including IoT devices and phenology applications. By combining real-time data with advanced processing, the platform supports short-term decision-making and adaptive strategies in viticulture. Three main objectives are fulfilled: (1) identification of the necessity

for a unified platform in Montenegrin viticulture; (2) architecture and functionality of the DSP; (3) sustainability and scalability of the DSP.

The following points emphasize what differentiates our DSP from existing solutions:

- Unlike previous decision support systems that focus on isolated vineyard management aspects, our DSP integrates IoT-enabled climate data, phenological modelling, and predictive analytics in a unified framework.
- A structured multi-layered architecture that ensures data harmonization and real-time adaptability to viticultural challenges posed by climate change is introduced.
- The platform enables multi-level stakeholder collaboration, bridging the gap between vineyard managers, researchers, and policymakers, a key missing element in viticulture-focused DSS.
- Proposed approach incorporates high-resolution localized climate data, overcoming the spatial limitations of widely used global datasets (e.g., CHELSA, ERA5-Land, E-OBS) through advanced downscaling techniques.
- A sustainability plan to ensure long-term viability beyond the project scope, addressing a common issue with technology-driven research initiatives in agriculture is proposed.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Towards a Structured Framework for Data Management

In achieving sustainable vineyard management, it is essential to establish a systematic and structured approach to handling diverse and complex datasets [43,45,46]. Montenegro's viticulture sector faces significant barriers in adapting to climate change and improving operational efficiency due to the fragmented nature of its current data management practices. Key information related to microclimatic conditions, grapevine growth patterns, and soil characteristics often exists in isolated systems, limiting its practical application in vineyard decision-making. This fragmentation is further compounded by the inadequacies of global climate datasets, which, while providing valuable large-scale insights, often lack the granularity needed for Montenegro's topographically diverse landscape.

A structured framework for vineyard data management should ensure effective utilization of data for optimizing vineyard operations, improving crop quality, and supporting decision-making. To achieve this, various approaches are presented in the literature [47–51]. However, each country has its own specificities in terms of end-user requirements and legal regulations that influences both data availability and data collection. Since Montenegro does not have a unified approach in handling vineyard and climate datasets, and it is in the process of harmonizing it with European practices, the data management framework should be established in a such a way to incorporate current requirements and at the same time be flexible for the implementation of new strategies.

The DSP development methodology has considered the common design steps in the development of such systems that include: (1) the identification of end-users/stakeholders, and (2) their functional and non-functional requirements, (3) the identification of required and available data sources, (4) definitions of data sharing rules and security policies, (5) the development of the system architecture, (6) the development of the implementation and sustainability plan. We paid special attention to the platform's sustainability plan, because experience has shown us that most systems that are developed through projects only last a few years after the project ends.

This integrated framework goes beyond merely combining datasets. It allows for real-time data updates, improving responsiveness to changing environmental and operational conditions. Additionally, its adaptability ensures that new data sources or predictive models can be incorporated as they become available. The result is a dynamic and scalable platform that can evolve alongside the sector's needs and technological advancements.

By enabling the seamless sharing of information across stakeholders, this approach fosters collaboration and transparency. It empowers decision-makers with reliable, actionable insights tailored to specific challenges and objectives, whether optimizing irrigation strategies at the local level or informing sustainability policies at a national scale. Ultimately, this structured framework provides the foundation for advancing sustainable viticulture in Montenegro by bridging gaps in knowledge, improving resource efficiency, and enhancing resilience against the impacts of climate change.

2.2. Data Integration and Sharing

The effectiveness of a DSP in viticulture relies heavily on the integration of diverse data sources that provide comprehensive insights into vineyard conditions. In Montenegro, the proposed system incorporates several key sources of data, each addressing specific needs within vineyard management. IoT-enabled devices, such as climate sensors deployed in vineyards, provide localized, real-time data on environmental factors crucial for viticulture. These sensors monitor parameters including temperature, humidity, precipitation, wind speed and direction, solar radiation, and soil moisture [52,53]. The integration of IoT technology in vineyards facilitates precision viticulture, enabling optimized irrigation, disease prevention, and improved grape quality [54]. These devices provide precise data that capture microclimatic variations, essential for managing small, geographically diverse vineyards.

In addition to localized IoT data, global climate datasets like CHELSA contribute broader climate projections that help understand regional and global trends. However, while these datasets offer valuable context, their limited spatial resolution poses challenges for application in Montenegro's complex terrain. The platform bridges this gap by combining these large-scale datasets with localized IoT data, resulting in more accurate and actionable insights. Furthermore, research-based data, such as phenological observations, adds critical insights into grapevine development and responses to environmental stressors.

The sharing of this data operates across three levels: local, regional, and policy. At the local level, vineyard managers can utilize real-time data to make informed decisions regarding irrigation, pest control, and crop management, ensuring more efficient use of resources. At the regional level, aggregated data provides a broader understanding of climatic patterns and shared challenges, enabling cooperatives and associations to coordinate strategies and share resources effectively. Finally, at the policy level, comprehensive datasets inform evidence-based policy design and facilitate long-term planning, supporting the development of resilient and sustainable viticulture practices.

The benefits of this multi-level data sharing extend to all stakeholders. For vineyard managers, access to real-time and precise data enables operational efficiency and improved crop quality. Regional collaboration becomes more effective through the pooling of data, supporting coordinated responses to shared issues. At the policy level, robust datasets provide the foundation for crafting regulations and strategies that promote sustainability and climate resilience. By integrating diverse data sources and facilitating comprehensive sharing, the platform not only addresses immediate operational needs but also strengthens the overall ecosystem for sustainable vineyard management.

3. Results

3.1. System Architecture Design

The system architecture of the proposed DSP, illustrated in Figure 2, has been carefully crafted to address the diverse needs of stakeholders in viticulture. This modular design ensures flexibility, scalability, and adaptability, allowing the integration of various data sources and enabling multi-level decision-making processes. To provide a more structured

understanding of the framework, the inputs, data processing components, and outputs of the proposed DSP are explicitly defined. The effectiveness of the DSP is dependent on a diverse set of data inputs that represent both real-time and historical vineyard conditions. These include:

- IoT sensor data,
- phenological records,
- climate projections,
- soil properties and vineyard logs,
- regulatory and expert knowledge data.

Once collected, the data are processed within an integrated multi-layered architecture, ensuring consistency and usability for:

- data harmonization and preprocessing,
- AI-driven phenological and yield modelling,
- risk assessment and decision support analytics,
- geospatial integration and visualization.

Actionable insights are provided by the DSP outputs to three primary user categories:

- for vineyard managers, DSP offers real-time monitoring dashboards, along with automated alerts for weather-related risks and optimized recommendations for irrigation and disease management,
- for researchers, a structured data repository for viticulture–climate interactions is provided, enabling the validation of predictive models and long-term impact studies,
- for policymakers, data-driven reports on climate adaptation needs are created, sustainability impact assessments are offered, and policy recommendations for viticulture resilience are generated.

Figure 2. System architecture design.

The architecture is structured into interconnected layers, each tailored to overcome specific challenges in data collection, processing, analysis, and visualization, while fostering seamless collaboration among vineyard managers, researchers, and policymakers.

At the foundation of the DSP lies the Data Ingestion Layer, which serves as the primary entry point for integrating diverse information sources. This layer collects data from IoT-enabled sensors deployed in vineyards, global climate datasets, manually gathered field observations, and national regulatory databases. IoT sensors provide real-time, high-resolution data on environmental parameters such as temperature, pressure, air and soil humidity, wind direction and speed, etc., offering localized insights into vineyard-specific microclimatic conditions. Complementing this localized information, global datasets such as CHELSA deliver broader contextual data, including long-term climate trends that shape vineyard management practices. Manually collected data, such as phenological observations or pest monitoring, enriches the dataset by adding human expertise and direct field input. National legislative data ensures compliance with regulatory requirements, further supporting the sustainability and governance of vineyard operations.

The ingested data are stored and organized within the Permanent Storage Module, which provides a flexible framework for handling both structured and unstructured data. Relational databases like MySQL manage structured data, while NoSQL databases accommodate dynamic or less structured datasets. The Storage Data Manipulation Module processes the raw data, ensuring it is properly formatted, harmonized, and ready for further analysis. This approach guarantees efficient data retrieval and enables the system to handle the complexities of diverse data sources.

Once organized, the data flow into the Data Processing Layer, which functions as the analytical core of the platform. Here, advanced algorithms are applied to transform raw inputs into actionable insights. The Data Processing Module aligns and standardizes the datasets, removing inconsistencies and ensuring compatibility between diverse sources. This layer includes a Functionality Upgrade Module, allowing the architecture to evolve by integrating new tools, algorithms, or datasets as technological advancements emerge. The Decision Support Module is a key feature of this layer, combining statistical tools for trend analysis with artificial intelligence models for predictive analytics. For instance, the module forecasts phenological events such as flowering and ripening and predicts potential risks, such as pest outbreaks or water stress. These predictive capabilities empower vineyard managers to make proactive decisions, minimizing risks and optimizing operations.

The processed data are delivered to stakeholders through the Interface Layer (Front-end), which translates complex analyses into accessible, user-friendly formats. This layer includes a Data Customization and Security Module, allowing stakeholders to tailor data visualizations to their specific needs while ensuring the integrity and confidentiality of the information. The Data Interpretation Module presents results using intuitive formats such as interactive dashboards, geospatial maps, and reports, making it easier for stakeholders to understand and act on the insights provided by the system. In terms of information, this will be personalized, regarding the specific and personalized needs of each stakeholder. Geospatial information will have variable resolution, the lowest resolution will be for down-scaled climate data with 1 km resolution, using the CHELSA algorithm as example [55–57]. Additionally, the API Module facilitates seamless integration with external systems, enabling compatibility with third-party tools and legacy software.

The final stage of the system architecture involves End-User Applications, which deliver tailored solutions for different stakeholder groups. For vineyard managers, applications provide real-time monitoring of vineyard conditions, with alerts for immediate action when critical thresholds are reached. Policymakers benefit from aggregated regional data and long-term projections, enabling them to design evidence-based policies and sustainability strategies. Researchers gain access to detailed datasets, supporting advanced modeling and the development of innovative solutions for vineyard management challenges.

This interconnected architecture is designed to bridge gaps in data availability, harmonization, and accessibility, creating a centralized ecosystem that supports evidence-based decision-making. Its modularity ensures adaptability, allowing the system to evolve in response to changing stakeholder needs and technological advancements. The DSP not only addresses immediate operational challenges but also provides a scalable model for achieving long-term sustainability and climate resilience in vineyard management, particularly in Montenegro and similar regions facing complex environmental and resource constraints.

3.2. Implementation Strategies

The successful deployment of the DSP in Montenegro requires a systematic approach that addresses both technical and logistical challenges while ensuring stakeholder engagement. Implementation begins with the establishment of pilot projects to test the platform in real-world conditions and refine its functionality. Representative vineyards, selected based on geographic and climatic diversity, serve as testing grounds for IoT sensors and the initial integration of data sources. These sensors provide localized, real-time environmental data, offering valuable insights into microclimatic variations specific to Montenegro's unique terrain.

The Data Integration Module handles the transformation of data from external sources into formats compatible with the Data Processing Layer. Additionally, it incorporates a metadata header that includes data ontology, access controls, and sharing policies. Data transaction requests can originate either from this module or from external data sources. When a data source initiates the connection, the platform dictates the communication and data exchange protocols, requiring the external server to adapt. The platform employs a standardized RESTful API for such exchanges. A common example involves data exchange with sensor nodes deployed in the field. After acquiring sensor data, the data are formatted in JSON and transmitted via standardized HTTPS requests to the cloud platform.

For data exchanges initiated by the cloud platform, the Data Integration Module adapts its messages to protocols understood by the external server hosting the data. Since different servers may use varying communication protocols, dedicated microservices are developed for each case. These microservices are customizable, allowing the user to implement data transformation algorithms to ensure compatibility with the Data Processing Layer. A typical scenario involves retrieving data from a weather service, where the service's specific API governs data exchange.

Combining localized data collected by IoT devices with global datasets requires the harmonization of data formats and the alignment of temporal and spatial resolutions. This step ensures that the platform can provide accurate and actionable insights, bridging the gap between large-scale climate projections and localized vineyard conditions, through downscaling using the CHELSA algorithm, as an example [55–57]. Advanced algorithms should be employed to process and standardize the data, enabling seamless integration across diverse sources. Aligning datasets with different temporal and spatial (geographical) resolutions is crucial. Temporal alignment may involve resampling data to a common time interval (e.g., daily averages), while spatial alignment might require interpolating data to a consistent grid size. Techniques such as downscaling are employed to refine coarse-resolution global climate data to match the finer resolution of local IoT sensor data, enhancing the relevance of climate projections for specific vineyard locations [58]. Integrating global climate models with local sensor data involves data fusion methods that combine multiple data sources to produce more comprehensive insights. Machine learning (ML) algorithms, such as deep learning models, can be trained to recognize patterns across scales, enabling the translation of large-scale climate information into localized predictions relevant to vineyard management. Due to their ability to apply non-linear approximation,

ML models outperform statistical models in terms of predictive performance. Moreover, they are often characterized by greater flexibility and adaptability to shifts in environmental conditions and can be trained to learn from large datasets. This makes them particularly effective in handling the spatiotemporal expansion of drought for example, which can be challenging for other models [59].

Stakeholder training is another critical component of the deployment strategy. Vineyard managers, researchers, and policymakers need to receive tailored training sessions to familiarize them with the platform's features and capabilities. This training emphasizes practical use cases, such as interpreting data visualizations, generating predictive models, and leveraging insights for decision-making. By equipping stakeholders with the necessary skills and knowledge, the platform's adoption and effectiveness are significantly enhanced. To ensure continuous improvement and adaptability, it is important to establish feedback mechanisms. Stakeholders are encouraged to share their experiences, challenges, and suggestions for improvement. These feedback loops allow the platform to evolve in response to user needs, technological advancements, and emerging challenges. These regular updates and enhancements based on stakeholder input ensure the platform remains relevant and effective over time.

Several challenges are anticipated during the implementation process. One of the key technical challenges is ensuring the accuracy and compatibility of data collected by IoT sensors. Variability in sensor performance and data quality could hinder the reliability of insights generated by the platform. To address this, standardized protocols for data collection should be implemented, and sensors will undergo regular calibration to maintain accuracy. Additionally, robust data validation processes should be integrated into the platform to detect and mitigate inconsistencies.

Logistical challenges, such as securing stakeholder participation and long-term funding, also pose significant barriers. Vineyard managers and other stakeholders may initially hesitate to adopt the platform due to perceived complexity or uncertainty about its benefits. Funding sustainability is another critical concern, particularly in the context of long-term maintenance and expansion. To address this, partnerships with local and international organizations are explored, leveraging grants, subsidies, and private investments. The demonstrable benefits of the platform, combined with its potential for scalability, will serve as compelling arguments for securing financial support.

Financial support for implementing DSP in sustainable viticulture is structured across three key levels, as shown in Table 1. At the European Union level, programs such as Horizon Europe, the EU's primary research and innovation initiative, and the European Regional Development Fund (ERDF) provide essential funding to promote innovation and sustainability in agriculture. Notably, ERDF operations are expected to allocate 30% of their total funding to climate objectives. Furthermore, Interreg programs foster regional cooperation, with initiatives like Smart Viticulture for Rural Areas demonstrating the value of digital technologies in enhancing sustainability in rural viticulture.

At the national level, the Ministry of Agriculture and related authorities play a central role in ensuring the implementation and sustainability of the DSP. These institutions are responsible for overseeing its operation, providing consistent funding, and aligning its goals with broader national agricultural strategies. For instance, in Montenegro, the Agrobudget includes dedicated support measures for wine producers, such as restructuring vineyards, promoting wine, and adopting sustainable practices like green harvesting. These initiatives not only support the expansion of vineyard cultivation and the revitalization of abandoned vineyards but also adapt the wine industry to global market trends. Through its leadership, the Ministry can ensure continuous financing for the DSP, integrating it as a critical tool in national agricultural policy.

Finally, local collaborations with stakeholders, including regional agencies, research institutions, and vineyard managers, provide additional support. These partnerships foster expertise sharing and ensure the DSP remains responsive to the needs of end-users while being tailored to local challenges. By engaging with regional authorities and agricultural cooperatives, the DSP can achieve its long-term sustainability goals, extending its impact across the viticulture sector.

Table 1. Financial sustainability of the DSP.

Funding	Short-Term	Long-Term
EU funding	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
National R&D funding	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Ministry and Public Authorities support	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>

By placing the Ministry of Agriculture or equivalent national authorities at the forefront, this approach ensures the DSP’s continuous operation and financial sustainability. Their leadership and integration of the DSP into agricultural policy not only promote sustainable viticulture practices but also establish a model that can be adopted in other regions. This ensures the platform remains adaptable and impactful over the long term, addressing diverse user needs and driving innovation in viticulture.

3.3. Functionality of the DSP

The interconnected framework of the DSP, displayed in Figure 3, highlights how the platform unites researchers, winegrowers, and policymakers to foster collaboration and data-driven decision-making. By integrating diverse datasets and providing tailored insights, the DSP enables researchers to refine predictive models, winegrowers to optimize vineyard operations, and policymakers to develop evidence-based strategies. This holistic approach ensures that all stakeholders work together to tackle climate challenges, enhance sustainability, and improve resilience within the viticulture sector.

Figure 3. Interconnected data flow in the DSP.

Figure 4 presents a cyclic value chain, emphasizing the interconnections and bidirectional influences between the DSP's key stakeholders. Each arrow in the graph represents a specific flow of influence or interaction, highlighting how these stakeholders collaborate to address challenges and enhance sustainability in viticulture.

Winegrowers and researchers share a symbiotic relationship. Winegrowers provide researchers with critical vineyard data and insights, such as environmental conditions and operational practices. In return, researchers deliver predictive models and operational advice tailored to vineyard-specific needs, enabling winegrowers to optimize their management practices. This exchange ensures that practical challenges in the field inform research while scientific advancements directly benefit vineyard operations.

The connection between winegrowers and policymakers reflects a similar bidirectional influence. Winegrowers contribute feedback on the impacts of regulations and policies, ensuring that ground-level realities are considered in policy-making processes. Policymakers, in turn, establish agricultural policies and incentives that guide sustainable practices, fostering resilience and efficiency in vineyard operations. This interplay underscores the importance of aligning policy initiatives with the practical needs of the viticulture sector.

Researchers and policymakers also maintain a crucial two-way interaction. Researchers deliver comprehensive analyses of climate trends, phenological patterns, and long-term environmental impacts to policymakers. This information supports the development of evidence-based policies that address pressing challenges in viticulture. Policymakers provide funding and prioritize research efforts, shaping the focus and resources available to researchers for exploring innovative solutions.

Figure 4. Dynamic value chain of stakeholder interactions in the DSP.

The DSP is designed to provide comprehensive tools and functionalities to support data-driven decision-making in viticulture. Its core functionality lies in its ability to integrate and harmonize diverse data sources, enabling seamless access to reliable and actionable insights. The platform collects information from IoT sensors deployed in vineyards and global climate databases in the form of phenological data. By harmonizing these diverse data streams, the DSP ensures that users have access to accurate, real-time data tailored to specific vineyard conditions.

The DSP features intuitive visualization tools that simplify complex datasets, making them accessible and actionable for diverse stakeholders. Through interactive dashboards, geospatial mapping, and tailored alerts, users can monitor critical parameters and take timely actions. For instance, vineyard managers can analyze temperature fluctuations and adjust canopy management practices to protect grape quality during heatwaves, while policymakers can utilize regional climate projections to develop policies that enhance climate resilience across the viticulture sector.

Beyond data analysis and visualization, the DSP offers tailored decision support recommendations. These insights are customized based on local conditions, regional trends, and policy objectives, ensuring that the platform serves the unique needs of its diverse users. For vineyard managers, this might involve specific advice on irrigation, pruning, or pest control, while policymakers receive evidence-based recommendations for crafting regulations and sustainability initiatives.

The modular design of the DSP ensures scalability and adaptability, making it suitable for a wide range of contexts and evolving user needs. As new data sources or analytical tools become available, they can be seamlessly integrated into the platform, ensuring its continued relevance and effectiveness. By combining data integration, predictive modeling, visualization, and decision support, the DSP serves as a powerful tool for advancing sustainable viticulture practices and improving collaboration among stakeholders. This comprehensive suite of functionalities also supports long-term planning and innovation, making the DSP an essential resource for modern vineyard management.

The DSP provides numerous benefits across the viticulture value chain, significantly improving operational efficiency and long-term sustainability. By fostering an interconnected approach, it promotes collaboration among stakeholders, providing each with tailored insights and tools to address their specific needs. Table 2 presents a structured analysis of the benefits provided by the DSP to its stakeholders: winegrowers, researchers, and policymakers. Each benefit highlights how the platform meets the distinct needs of these groups while fostering collaboration and efficiency across the viticulture ecosystem. Winegrowers are among the primary beneficiaries of the DSP due to their direct reliance on data for operational decision-making. The platform provides them with real-time data that are essential for monitoring environmental conditions and addressing vineyard-specific challenges promptly. This capability enhances their resource efficiency by optimizing the use of water, fertilizers, and other inputs, significantly reducing waste and costs. Winegrowers gain access to advanced predictive modelling tools, allowing them to anticipate critical vineyard events such as phenological stages or pest outbreaks. These insights enable them to implement preventive measures and adjust management practices, ensuring a proactive rather than reactive approach. Through tailored recommendations, such as irrigation schedules or pest control strategies, the DSP ensures that its guidance aligns with the unique conditions of each vineyard. The integration of diverse datasets allows winegrowers to benefit from a broader context, as the platform harmonizes localized data with regional and global insights, enabling more informed decisions. For researchers, the DSP is a transformative tool consolidating various data streams into a centralized repository. This feature facilitates advanced studies and innovations, as researchers can access high-quality datasets, including real-time environmental data, phenological records, and global climate projections. The platform's predictive modelling capabilities also support researchers in refining algorithms and developing new solutions for sustainable vineyard management. Monitoring regional trends and analyzing long-term climate impacts enables researchers to contribute valuable insights to the broader understanding of viticulture under changing environmental conditions. The DSP's advanced visualization tools, such as dashboards and geospatial mapping, further empower researchers by simplifying complex datasets,

making them more accessible for analysis and presentation. Policymakers also benefit significantly from the DSP's functionalities. The platform offers a robust foundation for evidence-based policy formulation by integrating diverse datasets and presenting comprehensive insights. These insights are crucial for designing regulations and sustainability initiatives that address both immediate operational needs and long-term strategic goals. Policymakers can leverage the platform's ability to monitor regional trends and climate resilience strategies, ensuring that policies are aligned with ground realities and future challenges. The DSP fosters collaboration between policymakers and other stakeholders, creating an interconnected ecosystem where knowledge flows seamlessly and informed decisions are made collectively. The platform supports long-term climate impact analysis, helping policymakers craft adaptive strategies that enhance resilience in the viticulture sector. The DSP's capacity for integration and scalability ensures that its benefits extend across all stakeholder groups; by harmonizing diverse datasets and providing a unified interface, the platform bridges gaps in data accessibility and usability. Its modular design allows for the seamless incorporation of new tools and datasets, ensuring its relevance in evolving technological landscapes. The intuitive visualization tools enable all stakeholders, regardless of their expertise, to interpret complex data and take appropriate actions. Stakeholder training programs facilitated by the DSP further enhance its adoption and utility, empowering users with the skills needed to maximise their potential.

Table 2. DSP benefits for different stakeholder groups.

Benefits	Winegrowers	Researchers	Policymakers
Access to real-time data	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Enhanced predictive modeling	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Improved resource efficiency	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Optimization of vineyard operations	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Improved collaboration across stakeholders	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Evidence-based policy formulation	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Tailored recommendations for vineyard management	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Integration of diverse datasets	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Development of climate resilience strategies	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Long-term climate impact analysis	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Regional trend monitoring	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Real-time alerts for operational issues	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Cost reduction through optimized practices	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Access to high-quality, centralized datasets	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Scalable and adaptable platform integration	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Support for advanced research and innovation	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Data visualization through dashboards	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Facilitation of stakeholder training	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>

3.4. Data Workflow

The designed DSP is complex, but in terms of an input/output overview, Figure 5 illustrates the projected approach. Subdivided into four parts, input data, process, results and decision support, it is ceded to platform users the synthesized decision support information, and optionally the results. The input data includes sensor readings from

vineyards, weather station data maintained by the Institute of Hydrometeorology and Seismology of Montenegro, and observational datasets such as E-OBS [18] and ERA5-Land [19], and CHELSA-W5E5 [60]. These datasets allow us to correct and calibrate sensor data that can be decalibrated by local conditions, provide weather forecasts in the vineyards, and are also useful for climate data processing, for bias adjustment of climate projections [61]. Climate projection data are available from sources such as the Coupled Model Intercomparison Project Phase 6 (CMIP6) [62] and the third simulation phase of the Inter-Sectoral Impact Model Intercomparison Project (ISIMIP3b) [63], which incorporates the Shared Socio-Economic Pathways (SSPs). These can be downscaled to 1 km to properly portray Montenegro’s climate conditions due to the complex topography, with algorithms such as the CHELSA algorithm [55–57]. Alternatively, higher resolutions can be achieved by algorithms such as NicheMapR citex [64]. In this sequence, processed climate data serve as input for future phenology and yield modelling. Among these task–candidate approaches are ML [65], growing degree days and statistical models [66], and a generic soil crop model (STICS) [67]. The choice of the models, for each vineyard, is dependent on the available data, which comprises, yield, phenology and viticulture practices. Also, soil properties are necessary, at least for robust tools such as STICS. Preferably soil properties (for example: texture, water holding capacity), must be collected on-site, however, the Land Use and Coverage Area Frame Survey [68] and European Soil Database [69] can be used to provide soil property estimations. With all these inputs, it is possible to provide yield and phenology predictions to support wine growers, and conjunctly with bioclimatic indices, it is possible to cceed the suitable adaptation measures in each vineyard. Also, the real-time data provided by sensors supports optimizing vineyard management, providing short-term measures, crucial to develop sustainable yield and executing short-term operations, such as pruning. By storing and accumulating weather station data, it is also possible to monitor the climate trends, to adjust future decision support.

Figure 5. Input/output data overview.

4. Discussion

The DSP presented in this study advances precision viticulture by addressing the immediate and long-term challenges posed by climate variability and fragmented data management. Unlike conventional vineyard management systems, which primarily rely on manual observations and historical climate trends, the proposed DSP integrates real-time IoT-enabled data, predictive modeling, and stakeholder collaboration. Thus, it forms a knowledge-driven approach that bridges the gap between data acquisition, interpretation, and actionable decision-making.

In the broader field of precision viticulture, this DSP contributes significantly by incorporating AI-driven phenological modelling and high-resolution climate data harmonization. These elements enhance the accuracy of vineyard-specific risk assessments and climate adaptation strategies, ensuring more precise and context-aware decision-making. As the European Union intensifies its commitment to sustainable agriculture under policies such as the Farm to Fork Strategy and the EU Biodiversity Strategy for 2030 [14,15], the DSP aligns seamlessly with these objectives by enabling resource-efficient viticulture and improved environmental resilience. Furthermore, the platform's data-sharing mechanisms support collaborative efforts within the European viticulture research community, fostering cross-regional knowledge exchange and strengthening policy-driven interventions for climate adaptation in viticulture.

A key distinction of this DSP from existing DSS in viticulture lies in its multi-layered data fusion capability and predictive modelling approach. Current DSS solutions often focus on individual aspects of vineyard management, such as irrigation control [42] or disease prediction [41], without fully integrating climate projections, phenological modelling, and stakeholder-driven decision support. This limitation hinders their ability to provide holistic, scalable solutions for sustainable viticulture. The proposed DSP advances the field by bridging these gaps, incorporating both large-scale climate models and microclimate sensor data while offering an adaptive architecture that can be customized for different vineyard conditions.

Transitioning from a framework to full-scale implementation requires a structured approach, including pilot deployments in diverse vineyard settings, iterative validation through field data integration, and the refinement of predictive algorithms based on real-world vineyard responses. Future research should focus on integrating additional machine learning techniques to enhance predictive accuracy, as well as developing real-time feedback mechanisms for adaptive vineyard management. Furthermore, collaboration with EU-funded research programs, such as Horizon Europe projects focusing on agricultural resilience, will facilitate both funding opportunities and interdisciplinary research engagement. These efforts will ensure that the DSP moves beyond conceptual development into a fully operational decision-support infrastructure that benefits viticulture stakeholders at multiple levels.

By establishing a robust data-sharing and stakeholder engagement ecosystem, the DSP lays the foundation for a scalable and replicable model that can be adapted to other wine-producing regions facing similar climatic and environmental challenges. The integration of sustainability-driven decision support and real-time operational intelligence positions this DSP as a transformative tool for viticulture, advancing both scientific innovation and practical vineyard management strategies.

The DSP is designed to serve as a central hub, bringing together researchers, winegrowers, and policymakers into a unified ecosystem. By fostering collaboration, it ensures that all stakeholders have access to the same reliable, high-quality data, which reduces fragmentation and duplication of efforts. Researchers benefit from a centralized repository of climate and phenological data that can support advanced studies and predictive

modeling. Winegrowers, in turn, receive actionable insights derived from research and data analytics, enabling them to make better operational decisions. Policymakers are provided with the evidence base necessary for crafting data-driven regulations and strategies that address the broader needs of the viticulture sector. This interconnected system not only enhances individual productivity and outcomes, but also creates synergies that drive collective progress.

For our platform, the biggest challenge is predicted to be the grapevine modelling. Among all necessary data inputs, phenology and yield are the most crucial for efficient model calibration [70]. Still, as one of the project goals is to keep track of phenological phases across different grape varieties in vineyards, this task will become easier with the engagement of grape growers.

The platform is closely aligned with the principles of sustainability, addressing critical challenges such as resource efficiency, climate resilience, and environmental conservation. By optimizing the use of water, fertilizers, and other resources, it minimizes waste and reduces the environmental impact of vineyard operations. The integration of high-resolution data with predictive tools helps mitigate risks associated with climate variability, enabling proactive adaptation to changing conditions. Moreover, the platform emphasizes collaboration and knowledge-sharing, fostering a culture of sustainable practices throughout the viticulture ecosystem. From operational efficiencies at the vineyard level to informed policy interventions, the DSP contributes to building a resilient and environmentally responsible viticulture sector.

In Montenegro, the implementation of the DSP addresses pressing challenges while fostering innovation and sustainability. Through precise, data-driven recommendations, the platform ensures judicious application of water, fertilizers, and other inputs, aligning with the broader goals of sustainable agriculture. These practices balance productivity with environmental conservation, minimizing waste and reducing the sector's overall environmental footprint. Additionally, the system's ability to generate actionable insights represents a key advantage. By integrating localized data with global datasets and predictive models, it delivers real-time guidance on essential operations such as irrigation scheduling and pest management. This localized yet scalable approach empowers vineyard managers, cooperative organizations, and policymakers to identify shared challenges and coordinate their responses effectively.

Collaboration remains a cornerstone of the DSP's impact. The platform bridges gaps between research, practice, and policy, fostering a cohesive ecosystem where stakeholders work in tandem. Researchers benefit from access to high-quality data repositories that streamline analyses and support innovation. Winegrowers gain valuable tools and shared knowledge to enhance operational efficiency. Policymakers, armed with robust datasets, are better equipped to design adaptive regulations that address on-the-ground realities. This interconnected approach strengthens the overall resilience of the sector, creating a foundation for sustainable and adaptive vineyard management.

Decision support platforms in the scope of viticulture have wide applications, from cultivation to the sale of final products, as example platforms for data aggregation and usage of AI to increase customer engagement [71]. In the scope of grape growing, it is necessary to use cost-effective sensors, allowing for more sensors across multiple vineyards, and providing real-time data [72]. Sensors can measure various parameters such as air quality, weather conditions, and pest presence, enabling proactive farm management [73]. Platforms such as mySense, developed in Portugal [74] are examples of such an approach. However, in the author's perspective, it is necessary to develop local platforms, which allow for greater engagement with local users. Also, providing Webgis features [75] is inclusive for GIS-familiar users, supporting precision viticulture. Nowadays, the inclusion

of remote sensing in the platform is necessary for short-term decision support in vineyard management [76].

The integral approach to modelling DSP represents a groundbreaking advancement, as it transcends traditional, isolated methods by fostering an interconnected ecosystem that impacts not only winegrowers but the entire value chain. By integrating diverse data sources, predictive analytics, and stakeholder collaboration, the DSP empowers winegrowers with actionable insights to optimize operations, improve resource efficiency, and enhance resilience to climate change. Beyond the vineyard, this interconnected framework influences researchers by streamlining access to high-quality data for innovation and policy-makers by providing evidence-based guidance for crafting adaptive strategies. The holistic nature of this system ensures that decisions made at any point in the value chain cascade throughout, creating a synergistic effect that elevates sustainability, collaboration, and innovation across all levels of viticulture. This transformative approach ensures that the DSP not only addresses immediate operational challenges but also catalyses systemic improvements, marking a significant advancement toward a more resilient and sustainable viticulture ecosystem.

5. Conclusions

Unlike existing DSS solutions, which are often constrained by localized, single-purpose applications, the proposed DSP introduces a comprehensive, multi-layered approach that harmonizes real-time sensor data with large-scale climate models. This allows for the generation of adaptive decision support tailored to vineyard-specific needs, reinforcing the transition towards precision viticulture. The DSP's modular design ensures that it remains flexible and scalable, capable of incorporating future advancements in viticulture technology, climate science, and artificial intelligence.

A key aspect of this research is its alignment with broader EU sustainability policies, such as the Common Agricultural Policy, the Green Deal objectives, and Horizon Europe's research directives on climate adaptation. The DSP is designed not only as an operational tool for vineyard managers but also as a research-oriented platform that enhances scientific exploration in viticulture–climate interactions. Its data-sharing structure fosters cross-regional collaboration, allowing for the development of standardized approaches to viticulture adaptation across different European wine-producing regions.

Future research efforts should focus on implementing and testing the DSP in real-world vineyard environments, ensuring that its predictive analytics and AI-driven models are validated under diverse climatic and geographical conditions. In particular, pilot projects should be deployed in regions with significant climate-induced viticulture risks, facilitating the refinement of its data-processing capabilities. Additionally, the integration of stakeholder-driven feedback mechanisms will be critical to adapting the platform's functionalities to practical vineyard management challenges.

By bridging the gap between viticultural expertise, real-time data analytics, and sustainability-driven policy-making, the DSP represents a transformative step towards a resilient and adaptive viticulture sector. This research establishes the foundation for future advancements in AI-enhanced decision support platforms in agriculture, reinforcing the role of precision viticulture in ensuring long-term environmental and economic sustainability.

This research marks a significant advancement in sustainable viticulture through the development and presentation of the DSP architecture. Specifically designed to address the challenges faced by Montenegro's vineyards, the DSP also offers a scalable model adaptable to other regions with similar conditions. By integrating diverse data sources, such as IoT-enabled sensors, global climate datasets, and research-based insights, the platform provides a centralized, data-driven decision-making tool tailored to the needs of viticulture.

Its predictive analytics, user-friendly visualization tools, and targeted decision support empower stakeholders across the entire value chain to optimize operations, improve resource efficiency, and foster seamless collaboration at every stage of vineyard management.

The DSP's design directly aligns with key sustainability goals, including improving resource utilization, minimizing environmental impact, and enhancing resilience to climate variability. By closing gaps in data accessibility and facilitating cross-sector collaboration, the platform creates an integrated ecosystem where knowledge flows seamlessly between vineyard operations, regional management, and policy development. This interconnected approach not only resolves immediate challenges in vineyard management but also establishes a foundation for long-term innovation, adaptability, and environmental stewardship.

The implementation of the DSP in Montenegro will demonstrate its practical viability and can serve as a benchmark for similar initiatives, particularly in smaller regions where limited resources and geographic diversity demand precision and innovation. Future development will focus on expanding the platform's scope by incorporating additional datasets, refining predictive models, and enhancing its applicability across diverse viticulture landscapes. By offering a replicable and impactful solution, this study contributes to the advancement of sustainable agriculture, bridging the gap between technology, viticulture, and environmental resilience.

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